

On Structural Properties of Soft Epigroups

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Abstract

Mathematical modelling has been developed for the solution of many complex problems that are incomplete and vagueness. One of these modelling is soft set theory, which has reached a very wide study potential in recent years. The soft set theory, proposed by Molodtsov, is seen as an effective mathematical tool to deal with uncertainty. This theory has been applied to various fields that involve uncertainty, such as information systems, decision-making problems, optimization theory, algebraic structures, and mathematical analysis. This study explores the interplay between soft set theory and the algebraic structure of epigroups by introducing the notion of soft epigroups. Foundational properties of soft epigroups are developed, along with key characterizations that underpin their structure. Furthermore, the study constructs the category of soft epigroups, providing a categorical framework for their analysis. The concept of soft subepigroup is also introduced, and several structural properties pertaining to these substructures are investigated in detail.

Keywords: Soft set, epigroup, subepigroup, soft epigroup, soft subepigroup

1. Introduction

Soft sets are a mathematical framework that extend classical set theory to handle uncertainty and vagueness in data and decision-making processes. Soft sets were introduced by Molodtsov in 1999 as a generalization of classical sets (Molodtsov, 1999). A soft set is a parameterized family of subsets of a universal set. Unlike fuzzy sets or rough sets, soft sets do not require a membership function or boundary approximation. Instead, the uncertainty is modeled through a mapping between parameters and subsets of the universe, which makes soft sets both simple and flexible for many applications. The concept of soft set has been extended and applied to various fields such as algebra, topology, decision theory, and artificial intelligence (Zou and Xiao, 2008; Zahedi Khameneh and Kılıçman, 2019; Oguz, 2020; Alcantud et al., 2024.). One of the key aspects of soft set theory is the ability to define and manipulate operations between soft sets, such as union, intersection, complement and difference (Maji et al., 2003; Ali et al., 2009; Kazanci et al., 2010). These operations form the basis for developing algebraic structures, constructing soft decision models. Since their introduction, soft sets have been successfully integrated with various classical algebraic structures to develop their corresponding soft analogues. These include soft groups, soft rings, soft lattices, and, more recently, soft semigroups (Aktas and Cagman, 2007; Atagun and Sezgin, 2011; Oguz et al., 2019; Oguz et al., 2020; Rao, 2020). Such constructions aim to generalize and extend conventional algebraic frameworks in order to handle uncertainty, imprecision and parameter-dependence in a systematic manner. In particular, soft semigroups provide a flexible structure wherein each parameter defines a subsemigroup of a given semigroup, offering a richer algebraic environment for theoretical exploration and practical applications (Ali and Shabir, 2009; Ali et al., 2010). In semigroup theory, an epigroup is a generalization of a group and a semigroup that retains some group-like properties without requiring all elements to be invertible. Epigroups arise

naturally in the study of algebraic structures with partial symmetries and have applications in automata theory, formal languages, and the theory of regular semigroups. Epigroups were first introduced by Douglas Munn in 1961 under the name pseudoinvertible semigroups (Munn, 1961). Later research established them as generalizations of periodic semigroups, meaning that all finite semigroups fall into this category (Shevrin, 1995). The fundamental property that each element in an epigroup has a power belonging to a subgroup allows for deeper structural insights compared to classical semigroups. The study of epigroups has led to significant advancements in abstract algebra, particularly in ring theory, automata structures, and universal algebra (Shevrin, 2005). By generalizing classical semigroup concepts, epigroups provide new frameworks for understanding algebraic systems and their practical applications (Valery et al., 2003). Their structural properties facilitate research in broader mathematical domains, enhancing theoretical tools used in various fields. The study of algebraic structures has led to significant advancements in abstract algebra and semigroup theory. This study aims to introduce and develop the concept of soft epigroups by integrating soft set theory with the algebraic framework of epigroups. It seeks to explore the fundamental properties, operations, and structural aspects of soft epigroups, including the characterization of soft subepigroups. This new algebraic structure creates opportunities for both theory and practical use in areas where information is unclear, vague, or depends on different conditions.

2. Preliminaries

In this section some notions and results concerning soft sets and epigroups are presented, which will be used in the sequel. Let X be an initial universe set and E be a set of parameters. Furthermore, $P(X)$ denotes the power set of X and $A \subseteq E$. A soft set, as defined by Molodtsov, is defined as follows:

Definition 1

A pair (\mathcal{F}, A) is said to be a soft set over X , where \mathcal{F} is a mapping defined by

$$\mathcal{F}: A \rightarrow P(X)$$

Notice that a soft set over X is, in fact, a parametrized family of subsets of the universe X (Molodtsov, 1999).

Definition 2

Let (\mathcal{F}, A) and (\mathcal{G}, B) be two soft sets over the common universe X . Then, (\mathcal{F}, A) is said to be a soft subset of (\mathcal{G}, B) (i.e., $(\mathcal{F}, A) \tilde{\subseteq} (\mathcal{G}, B)$) if

- i. $A \subseteq B$,
- ii. $\mathcal{F}(a)$ and $\mathcal{G}(a)$ are identical approximations for all $a \in A$ (Maji et al., 2003).

Definition 3

The support of a soft set (\mathcal{F}, A) is defined as a set

$$Supp(\mathcal{F}, A) = \{a \in A: \mathcal{F}(a) \neq \emptyset\}.$$

If $Supp(\mathcal{F}, A)$ is not equal to the empty set, then (\mathcal{F}, A) is said to be non-null.

In the following, some generalizations are given some generalizations for the non-empty family $\{(\mathcal{F}_\alpha, A_\alpha) | \alpha \in I\}$ of soft sets over the common universe X (Kazanci et al., 2010).

Definition 4

The *restricted intersection* of the family $\{(\mathcal{F}_\alpha, A_\alpha) | \alpha \in I\}$ is defined by a soft set $(\mathcal{F}, A) = \widetilde{\bigcap_{\alpha \in I} (\mathcal{F}_\alpha, A_\alpha)}$ such that $A = \bigcap_{\alpha \in I} A_\alpha \neq \emptyset$ and $\mathcal{F}(\alpha) = \bigcap_{\alpha \in I} \mathcal{F}_\alpha(\varepsilon)$ for all $\varepsilon \in A_\alpha$ (Kazanci et al., 2010).

Definition 5

The *extended intersection* of the family $\{(\mathcal{F}_\alpha, A_\alpha) | \alpha \in I\}$ is a soft set $(\mathcal{F}, A) = (\bigcap_{\varepsilon} \mathcal{F}_\alpha, A_\alpha)$ such that $A = \bigcup_{\alpha \in I} A_\alpha$ and $\mathcal{F}(\varepsilon) = \bigcap_{\alpha \in I(\varepsilon)} \mathcal{F}_\alpha(\varepsilon)$, $I(\varepsilon) = \{\alpha \in I | \varepsilon \in A_\alpha\}$ for all $\varepsilon \in A_\alpha$ (Kazanci et al., 2010).

Definition 6

Let S be non-empty sets. Then we call the pair $(S, *)$ as a semigroup, if there exists a binary operation:

$$*: S \times S \rightarrow S$$

such that the following condition holds:

$$a * (b * c) = (a * b) * c \text{ for all } a, b, c \in S.$$

We mostly omit it typographically, i.e. we write S instead of $(S, *)$.

Definition 7

A semigroup $(S, *)$ is said to be a commutative semigroup if the following condition holds

$$: a * b = b * a \text{ for all } a, b \in S.$$

Definition 8

Let $(S, *)$ and (T, \cdot) be semigroups, and $h: S \rightarrow T$ a mapping between them. The mapping h is called a homomorphism if it preserves the semigroup operation,

$$\text{i.e., } h(a * b) = h(a) \cdot h(b)$$

for all $a, b \in S$.

Homomorphisms that are injective (one-to-one) are called embeddings or monomorphisms, and those that are surjective (onto) are called epimorphisms. If a homomorphism is both injective and surjective, i.e., bijective, it is called an isomorphism.

Remark 1

Homomorphisms preserve these structures in the sense that the image of a subsemigroup under a homomorphism is again a subsemigroup; similarly, the preimage of a subsemigroup is a subsemigroup, provided it is non-empty. These properties make homomorphisms fundamental in analyzing the algebraic structure of semigroups. Epigroups play an important role in the study of algebraic structures and can be seen as a generalization of semigroups. An epigroup is a set with a binary operation that satisfies certain properties. This operation typically defines the relations and transformations among the elements of the epigroup.

Definition 9

A semigroup S is called an epigroup if, for any $a \in S$, there exists a positive integer n such that a^n is a group element, that is, belongs to a subgroup of S (Shevrin, 2005).

Definition 10

A subepigroup of an epigroup is a subsemigroup that is itself epigroup. (Liu, 2013).

Proposition 1

The centralizer of any subset of an epigroup is a subepigroup (Shevrin, 1995).

Definition 11

A semigroup homomorphism ϕ of an epigroup onto another epigroup is an epigroup homomorphism i.e.,

$$\phi(\bar{a}) = \overline{\phi(a)} \text{ for all } a \in S \text{ (Liu, 2013).}$$

Corollary 1

A homomorphic image of an epigroup is an epigroup (Liu, 2013).

3. Soft Epigroups

This section aims to establish a foundational understanding of soft epigroups and their associated characteristics.

Definition 12

Let \mathcal{V} be epigroup and (\mathcal{F}, A) denotes a non-null soft set over \mathcal{V} . Then, a pair (\mathcal{F}, A) is called a soft epigroup over \mathcal{V} , where \mathcal{F} is a mapping given by

$$\mathcal{F}: A \rightarrow P(\mathcal{V}) \text{ if}$$

$\mathcal{F}(a)$ is a subepigroup of \mathcal{V} for all $a \in A$.

Remark 2

The above definition shows that a soft epigroup (\mathcal{F}, A) can be determined as a parameterized family of subepigroups of the epigroup \mathcal{V} .

Example 1

Let \mathcal{V} be epigroup and W be non-empty subset of \mathcal{V} . Then, the mapping

$$\mathcal{F}: W \rightarrow P(\mathcal{V})$$

is defined by $\mathcal{F}(a) = Z(W)$ for all $a \in W$ such that $Z(W)$ is centralizer of W . It is easy to verify that $Z(W)$ is the subepigroup of \mathcal{V} . Hence, (\mathcal{F}, W) is a soft epigroup over \mathcal{V} .

Theorem 1

Let $\{(\mathcal{F}_i, A_i) \mid i \in \mathfrak{X}\}$ be a non-empty collection of soft epigroups over \mathcal{V} .

ii. The restricted intersection of the collection $\{(\mathcal{F}_i, A_i) \mid i \in \mathfrak{X}\}$ with $\bigcap_{i \in \mathfrak{X}} A_i \neq \emptyset$ is a soft epigroup over \mathcal{V} if it is non-null. **ii.** The extended intersection of the collection

$\{(\mathcal{F}_i, A_i) \mid i \in \mathfrak{X}\}$ is a soft epigroup over \mathcal{V} if it is non-null.

Proof

i. The restricted intersection of the collection $\{(\mathcal{F}_i, A_i) \mid i \in \mathfrak{X}\}$ with $\bigcap_{i \in \mathfrak{X}} A_i \neq \emptyset$ defined by the soft set $\overline{\bigcap_{i \in \mathfrak{X}} (\mathcal{F}_i, A_i)} = (\mathcal{F}, A)$ such that $\bigcap_{i \in \mathfrak{X}} \mathcal{F}_i(a)$ for all $a \in \mathcal{S}$. Choose $a \in \text{Supp}(\mathcal{F}, A)$. Together with the hypothesis, $\bigcap_{i \in \mathfrak{X}} \mathcal{F}_i(a) \neq \emptyset$, implies that $\mathcal{F}_i(a) \neq \emptyset$ for all $i \in \mathfrak{X}$. Since $\{(\mathcal{F}_i, A_i \mid i \in \mathfrak{X}\}$ is a non-empty family of soft epigroups over \mathcal{V} , it is then straightforward to ascertain that $\mathcal{F}_i(a)$ is a subepigroup of \mathcal{V} for all $i \in \mathfrak{X}$. In addition, $\bigcap_{i \in \mathfrak{X}} \mathcal{F}_i(a)$ is a subepigroup of \mathcal{V} too. Hence, (\mathcal{F}, A) is a soft epigroup over \mathcal{V} .

ii. As with the previous case, the proof can be considered analogous.

Definition 13

Let (\mathcal{F}_1, A) and (\mathcal{F}_2, B) are two soft epigroup over \mathcal{V}_1 and \mathcal{V}_2 , resp., let $\phi: A \rightarrow B$ and $\varphi: \mathcal{V}_1 \rightarrow \mathcal{V}_2$ be two mappings. In this case, the pair (φ, ϕ) is called a soft epigroup homomorphism if the following axioms hold:

i. φ is an epigroup epimorphism,

ii. ϕ is surjective,

ii. $\varphi(\mathcal{F}_1(a)) = \mathcal{F}_2(\phi(a))$ for all $a \in A$.

Note that if φ is an epigroup isomorphism and ϕ is bijective mapping, then (φ, ϕ) is called a soft epigroup isomorphism. In this direction, we obtain a new category whose objects are soft epigroup and whose arrows are soft epigroup homomorphisms.

Proposition 2

Let the pair (φ, ϕ) be a soft epigroup homomorphism between the soft epigroups (\mathcal{F}, A) and (\mathcal{S}, B) over \mathcal{V}_1 and \mathcal{V}_2 , resp. Then $(\varphi^{-1}(\mathcal{S}), A)$ is a soft epigroup over \mathcal{V}_1 if it is non-null.

Proof

Let (\mathcal{F}, A) and (\mathcal{S}, B) be two soft epigroups over \mathcal{V}_1 and \mathcal{V}_2 , respectively. Then it is easy to check that

$$\phi(\text{Supp}(\varphi^{-1}(\mathcal{S}), A) = \phi^{-1}(\text{Supp}(\mathcal{S}, B))$$

Taking $b \in \text{Supp}(\varphi^{-1}(\mathcal{S}), A)$, we get $\phi(b) \in \text{Supp}(\mathcal{S}, B)$. So, the non-empty set $\mathcal{S}(\phi(b))$ is a subepigroup of \mathcal{V}_2 . Also, since φ is an

epigroup homomorphism, we conclude that $\varphi^{-1}(\mathcal{S}(\phi(b))) = \varphi^{-1}(\mathcal{S}(b))$ is a subepigroup of \mathcal{V}_1 . This implies that $(\varphi^{-1}(\mathcal{S}), A)$ is a soft epigroup over \mathcal{V}_1 .

Definition 14

Let (\mathcal{F}, A) and (\mathcal{S}, B) be two soft epigroups over \mathcal{V} . If the following conditions are satisfied, then (\mathcal{S}, B) is said to be a soft subepigroup of (\mathcal{F}, A) :

- $B \subseteq A$,
- $\mathcal{S}(a)$ is a subepigroup $\mathcal{F}(a)$ for all $a \in \text{Supp}(\mathcal{S}, B)$.

Theorem 2

Let (\mathcal{F}, A) , (\mathcal{F}_1, B) and (\mathcal{F}_2, C) be any three soft epigroups over \mathcal{V} . If (\mathcal{F}_1, B) is a soft subepigroup of (\mathcal{F}, A) and (\mathcal{F}_2, C) is a soft subepigroup of (\mathcal{F}_1, B) , then (\mathcal{F}_2, C) is a soft subepigroup of (\mathcal{F}, A) .

Proof

Straightforward.

Proposition 3

Let (\mathcal{F}, A) and (\mathcal{S}, B) be two soft epigroups over \mathcal{V} . Then (\mathcal{S}, B) is a soft subepigroup of (\mathcal{F}, A) if (\mathcal{S}, B) is a soft subset of (\mathcal{F}, A) .

Proof

Assume that (\mathcal{F}, A) and (\mathcal{S}, B) are two soft epigroups over \mathcal{V} . Then, if (\mathcal{S}, B) is a soft subset of (\mathcal{F}, A) , we have $B \subseteq A$ and $\mathcal{S}(b) \subseteq \mathcal{F}(b)$ for all $b \in \text{Supp}(\mathcal{S}, B)$. It follows that $\mathcal{S}(b)$ is a subepigroup of $\mathcal{F}(b)$. Hence, (\mathcal{S}, B) is a soft subepigroup of (\mathcal{F}, A) .

The proposition outlined above gives rise to the following consequence:

Corollary 2

Let (\mathcal{F}, A) and (\mathcal{S}, A) be two soft epigroups over \mathcal{V} . Then (\mathcal{S}, A) is a soft subepigroup of (\mathcal{F}, A) if $\mathcal{S}(a) \subseteq \mathcal{F}(a)$ for all $a \in A$.

4. Conclusion

This study introduces a novel concept termed the soft epigroup, establishing a foundational relation between soft set theory and epigroup structures. By examining the properties of epigroups, the research aims to

bridge the gap between these two mathematical frameworks. The integration of epigroups with soft set theory aims to develop a comprehensive framework that leverages the strengths of both theories. By examining the properties of epigroups through the lens of soft sets, the research seeks to provide new insights and tools for handling complex algebraic structures under uncertainty. This interdisciplinary approach not only enriches the theoretical understanding of epigroups and soft sets but also opens avenues for practical applications where uncertainty and algebraic structures intersect.

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